

Effect of solvents on the reaction between ethyl α -halogenoacetate and triethylamine

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Second order rate constants for the reaction between ethyl α -halogenoacetate and triethylamine have been determined in aprotic dipolar ketonic solvents, aprotic dipolar halogenated and nitrogen-containing solvents, and alcoholic solvents at 30°. The simple and multiple regression of $\log k_2$ with various solvent parameters have been checked. It may be concluded that more than one interaction of solvent have to be considered to understand the effect of solvents on any reaction.

The Menshutkin salt is not formed in the reaction of phenacyl bromide with triethylamine in the presence of carboxylic acids in aprotic, protic and aqueous organic mixed solvents^{1,2}. In acetone, a facile reaction occurs between phenacyl bromide and carboxylic acid-triethylamine complex to yield phenacyl esters. Rate constants for the reaction of α -halogeno carbonyl compounds such as ethyl bromoacetate and triethylamine in a number of solvents at 30° has been determined. A plot of $\log k_2$ of $\text{BrCH}_2\text{COOEt} + \text{NEt}_3$ reaction vs $\log k_2$ of $\text{BrCH}_2\text{COPh} + \text{NEt}_3$ reaction is linear in some solvents³. Simple, dual and triple parameter correlations of $\log k_2$ at 30° for the reaction between $\text{BrCH}_2\text{COOEt}$ and NEt_3 with several solvent parameters at macroscopic and microscopic levels are found to be successful.

In general, quaternization reaction is very important reaction to study the effect of solvents since it is very sensitive to medium effect, easy to monitor and the mechanism is fairly well understood⁴. Though, it is known that reactions like Menshutkin type are accelerated by solvent polarity, quantitative correlation between $\log k_2$ and solvent parameter is still an elusive exercise. The current investigation involves the study of the effect of solvents by employing a variety of solvent parameters with a view to knowing the suitable correlation.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants of the reaction determined in various solvents at 30° (Table 1) are found comparable to that of

Table 1. Solvent parameters and $\log k_2$ values at 30° of reaction between NEt_3 and XCH_2COOEt *

$[\text{XCH}_2\text{COOEt}] = [\text{NEt}_3] = 0.025 \text{ M}$ (quaternization)

Solvent	ϵ	μ_D	$\frac{(\epsilon-1)}{(2\epsilon+1)}$	$\log k_2$ (n-Pr ₃ N + MeI)	E_T	π^*	$\frac{4 + \log k_2}{\text{XCH}_2\text{COOEt}$ (X = Br or I) + NEt ₃
Set-A (Aprotic dipolar ketonic solvents):							
Dimethylformamide	37.00	3.86	0.480	-0.222	43.8	0.88	3.493 (3.960)
Acetonitrile	35.95	3.92	0.479	-0.328	46.0	0.85	3.554 (4.009)
Acetone	20.70	2.88	0.465	-0.824	42.4	0.72	3.057 (3.446)
Methyl ethyl ketone	18.50	2.70	0.461	-1.099	41.3	0.67	2.964 (3.230)
Acetophenone	17.48	2.80	0.445	-0.377	41.3	0.90	-
3-Pentanone	17.00	2.50	0.444	-	39.3	-	3.053 (3.371)
Cyclohexanone	15.70	3.39	0.454	-0.796	39.8	0.76	3.111 (3.403)
2-Pentanone	15.40	2.50	0.439	-	41.1	-	3.412 (3.199)
Cyclopentanone	13.50	3.10	0.446	-0.658	40.8	0.75	-

Table-1(contd.)

Tetrahydrofuran	7.58	1.75	0.407	-1.538	37.4	0.58	- (3.137)
Ethyl acetate	6.02	1.88	0.358	-1.658	38.1	0.55	- (2.613)
Set-B (Aprotic dipolar halogenated and nitrogen containing solvents) :							
Nitromethane	35.87	3.56	0.473	0.041	46.3	0.85	3.879 (4.079)
Nitrobenzene	34.80	3.90	0.473	-0.319	42.0	1.01	-
2-Nitropropane	-	3.76	-	-	42.8	-	3.483 (3.561)
Nitroethane	28.06	3.60	0.466	-0.337	43.6	-	3.615 (3.805)
Propionitrile	27.20	3.57	0.465	-0.553	43.7	-	3.255 (3.667)
Benzonitrile	25.19	3.90	0.471	-0.409	42.0	0.90	3.312 (3.606)
1,2-Dichloroethane	10.30	1.85	0.431	-0.420	41.9	0.81	3.250 (3.459)
Dichloromethane	8.93	1.60	0.420	-0.553	41.1	0.80	3.029 (3.297)
Chlorobenzene	5.62	1.70	0.377	-1.155	37.5	0.71	-
Bromobenzene	5.40	1.52	0.344	-1.051	37.5	0.79	-
Chloroform	4.64	1.30	0.354	-0.886	39.1	0.76	-
Set-C (Protic hydroxylic solvents) :							
Methanol	32.70	2.87	0.470	-1.886	55.5	0.60	-
Ethanol	24.55	1.69	0.470	-2.022	51.9	0.54	2.114 -
Propan-1-ol	20.30	1.68	0.464	-2.131	50.7	0.51	2.114 (2.380)
Propan-2-ol	19.41	1.66	0.462	-	48.6	0.46	2.556 (2.643)
Butan-1-ol	17.51	1.65	0.458	-2.337	50.2	0.43	1.699 (1.903)
Butan-2-ol	15.80	1.71	0.454	-1.870	48.6	0.63	1.699 (2.000)
1,1-Dimethylethanol	12.50	1.66	0.440	-	43.9	0.41	2.146 (1.845)
3-Methylbutan-1-ol	14.70	1.80	0.450	-	47.0	-	2.114 (2.301)
2-Methoxyethanol	16.00	2.04	0.454	-	52.3	0.71	2.681 (2.763)
2-Ethoxyethanol	13.50	-	0.446	-	51.0	0.71	1.699 (2.491)
Benzyl alcohol	13.10	1.70	0.444	-1.237	50.8	0.98	2.908 (2.505)

* Values in parentheses are for the reaction of iodo compound; ϵ = dielectric constant, μ_D = dipole moment, $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ = Kirkwood function, $\log k_{2(n-Pr_3N + MeI)}$ = Lassau and Jungers solvent parameter at 20° scale,

E_T = transition energy for the intramolecular charge transfer band of the pyridinium phenol betain,

π^* : this scale is based on the solvent-induced shifts of the frequency maxima of the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of seven compounds.

$Et_3N + PhCOCH_2Br$ reaction⁶. This may be due to α -halogenocarbonyl compound used as a substrate in both the cases. Simple linear regression analysis was tried first and multiple regressions subsequently. Generally, dual param-

eter regression gives better results (Tables 2-4) than simple regression.

Among the dual parameter of treatments, the regression analysis with the parameter of $\log k_2$ vs Lassau and Jungers

Table 2. Simple regression of $\log k_2$ ($XCH_2COOEt + NEt_3$) vs solvent parameter for quaternization reaction*

$[XCH_2COOEt] = [NEt_3] = 0.025 M$, Temp. = 30°

Correlation	Set-A			Set-B			Set-C		
	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>
$\log k_2$ vs $1/\epsilon$	7 (9)	0.628 (0.867)	0.207 (0.226)	6 (6)	0.730 (0.857)	0.233 (0.157)	10 (9)	0.090 (0.200)	0.450 (0.799)
$\log k_2$ vs $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$	7 (9)	0.432 (0.891)	0.240 (0.206)	6 (6)	0.710 (0.832)	0.240 (0.169)	10 (9)	0.091 (0.230)	0.450 (0.343)
$\log k_2$ vs μ_D	7 (9)	0.640 (0.896)	0.204 (0.201)	7 (7)	0.610 (0.660)	0.243 (0.206)	9 (8)	0.384 (0.566)	0.410 (0.307)
$\log k_2$ vs $\log k_{(n-Pr_3N + Me)}$	5 (7)	0.972 (0.957)	0.073 (0.154)	6 (6)	0.925 (0.850)	0.130 (0.161)	5 (5)	0.842 (0.683)	0.307 (0.260)
$\log k_2$ vs E_T	7 (9)	0.736 (0.847)	0.180 (0.241)	7 (7)	0.885 (0.957)	0.143 (0.080)	10 (9)	0.154 (0.624)	0.447 (0.275)
$\log k_2$ vs π^*	5 (7)	0.964 (0.953)	0.082 (0.161)	-	-	-	9 (8)	0.471 (0.501)	0.425 (0.330)

*Values in the parentheses are for the reaction of $ICH_2COOEt + NEt_3$; *n* = number of solvents, *R* = regression coefficient, *S* = standard deviation.

Table 3. $\log k_2$ ($XCH_2COOEt + NEt_3$ reactions) – dual solvent parameter regression*

$[XCH_2COOEt] = [NEt_3] = 0.025 M$, Temp. = 30°

Correlation	Set-A			Set-B			Set-C		
	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>
$\log k_2$ vs Kirkwood function + μ_D	7 (9)	0.674 (0.933)	0.148 (0.164)	6 (6)	0.920 (0.963)	0.142 (0.091)	9 (8)	0.432 (0.657)	0.187 (0.202)
$\log k_2$ vs Kirkwood function + Lassau and Jungers $\log k_{(n-Pr_3N + Me)}$	5 (7)	0.976 (0.961)	0.080 (0.156)	6 (6)	0.964 (0.966)	0.101 (0.088)	5	0.868	0.301
$\log k_2$ vs Kirkwood function + E_T	7 (9)	0.814 (0.921)	0.140 (0.176)	6 (6)	0.909 (0.970)	0.149 (0.100)	10 (9)	0.248 (0.630)	0.116 (0.186)
$\log k_2$ vs Kirkwood function + π^*	5 (7)	0.981 (0.962)	0.071 (0.155)	-	-	-	9 (8)	0.484 (0.684)	0.220 (0.208)
$\log k_2$ vs Lassau and Jungers $\log k_{(n-Pr_3N + Me)} + \mu_D$	5 (7)	0.729 (0.969)	1.832 (0.141)	6 (6)	0.963 (0.961)	0.102 (0.094)	5	0.900	0.274
$\log k_2$ vs Lassau and Jungers $\log k_{(n-Pr_3N + Me)} + E_T$	5 (9)	0.985 (0.865)	0.064 (0.212)	6 (6)	0.958 (0.965)	0.108 (0.089)	5	0.961	0.185
$\log k_2$ vs Lassau and Jungers $\log k_{(n-Pr_3N + Me)} + \pi^*$	5 (7)	0.972 (0.963)	0.087 (0.153)	-	-	-	5	0.852	0.311

*Values in the parentheses are for the reaction of $ICH_2COOEt + NEt_3$; *n* = number of solvents, *R* = regression coefficient, *S* = standard deviation.

Table 4. $\log k_2$ ($XCH_2COOEt + NEt_3$ reactions) – triple solvent parameter regression*

$[XCH_2COOEt] = [NEt_3] = 0.025 M$, Temp. = 30°

Correlation	Set-A			Set-B			Set-C		
	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>
$\log k_2$ vs Kirkwood function + μ_D + Lassau and Jungers $\log k_{(n-Pr_3N + Me)}$	5 (7)	0.998 (0.973)	0.026 (0.152)	6 (6)	0.963 (0.972)	0.123 (0.097)	5	0.977	0.206
$\log k_2$ vs Kirkwood function + μ_D + E_T	7 (9)	0.928 (0.924)	0.012 (0.187)	6 (6)	0.930 (0.987)	0.164 (0.127)	9 (8)	0.572 (0.702)	0.246 (0.288)
$\log k_2$ vs Kirkwood function + μ_D + π^*	5 (7)	0.999 (0.825)	0.015 (0.435)	-	-	-	8 (7)	0.663 (0.791)	0.290 (0.255)
$\log k_2$ vs Lassau and Jungers $\log k_{(n-Pr_3N + Me)} + \mu_D + E_T$	5 (7)	0.998 (0.970)	0.027 (0.159)	6 (6)	0.971 (0.994)	0.111 (0.045)	5	0.975	0.212
$\log k_2$ vs Lassau and Jungers $\log k_{(n-Pr_3N + Me)} + \mu_D + \pi^*$	5 (7)	0.990 (0.974)	0.075 (0.148)	-	-	-	5	0.946	0.303

*Values in the parentheses are for the reaction of $ICH_2COOEt + NEt_3$; *n* = number of solvents, *R* = regression coefficient, *S* = standard deviation.

$\log k$ and E_T appears to give the best linearity for the solvent set A. In most of the cases, the confidence level exceeds 95%. From these observations, it may be concluded that more than one interaction of solvent have to be considered to understand the effect of solvents on the reaction.

Experimental

Ethyl bromoacetate (E. Merck) was used as such. Benzoic acid and triethylamine were purified by standard methods. Solvents used were purified as described in the literature.

Rate measurements : The conductivity method involving the Guggenheim principle⁵ was used. The experiments were carried out using an Elico P-E-133 pH meter. The conductivity cell was rinsed with conductivity water and then washed with acetone. A known volume of ethyl bromoacetate solution (10 ml; 0.05 M) and triethylamine solution (0.05 M; 25 ml) in the same solvent were kept in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) at 30° for ~ 1 h. After attaining thermal equilibrium, the conductance of the solutions was measured. A solution of NEt_3 (10 ml) was added to the ethyl bromoacetate solution and time was noted at the time of about half-addition. The conductivity cell was immediately placed in the reaction mixture and the conductance was noted as soon as possible. The rate constant k_2 was derived from the special integrated rate equation⁷ which was deduced using the Guggenheim principle.

Product analysis : Equal volumes of equimolar (0.05 M) solutions of ethyl bromoacetate and triethylamine in ace-

tone (50 ml) were mixed under kinetic reaction conditions. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and ethanol added to the residue. Ether was added till the appearance of the solid. It was kept in a freezing mixture for ~ 1 h. The purity of the resulting semi-solid was tested by tlc using methanol as eluent. The yield was $\sim 85\%$. The product was identified as ethoxycarbonylmethyltriethylammonium bromide on the basis of spectral data : ν_{\max} (nujol) (Bio-Rad FTS-7) 2900 (C-H aliphatic), 1700 (C-O ester), 1300 cm^{-1} (C-N); ^1H nmr (Bruker 200 MHz; CDCl_3) δ 1.24–1.20 (t, OCH_2CH_3), 1.40–1.33 (q, OCH_2CH_3), 3.76–3.65 (t, $\overset{+}{\text{N}}\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.25–4.14 (q, $\overset{+}{\text{N}}\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.40 (s, $\text{COCH}_2\overset{+}{\text{N}}$).

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